

The Effect of Methyl Substituent on the U. V. Spectra of some Aza-Aromatics

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The shift in the longest wavelength absorption band of methyl substituted Pyrazine, Pyrimidine, Pyridazine and Pyridine-1-oxide is theoretically calculated. The calculation shows fair agreement with experimentally determined values.

The effect of methyl substituent on the ultra violet spectra of alternant hydrocarbons has been discussed by Peters¹. As the inductive effect of a methyl group, represented by the change in coulomb integral of the carbon atom to which it is attached has little or no effect on the energy of $N \rightarrow V_1$ transition of alternant hydrocarbons, only the hyperconjugative effect was considered. However, as Chandra and Basu² pointed out, the inductive effect of a methyl group plays an important role in deciding the magnitude as well as the direction of the shifts in the longest wavelength ($N \rightarrow V_1$) band of aza-aromatics-pyridines. The present work is an extension of Chandra and Basu's² work and here both inductive and hyperconjugative effect have been considered.

The theoretical basis of the method has been discussed in detail by Longuet-Higgins and Sowden³. The principles are as follows :—

Inductive effect : The net change in the transition energy due to inductive effect is given by

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta E_{0a})_{\text{induc}} &\equiv (E'_b - E'_a) - (E_b - E_a) \\ &= (C_{br}^2 - C_{ar}^2) \delta\alpha_r + \left(\sum_{j \neq b} \frac{C_{br}^2 - C_{jr}^2}{E_b - E_j} - \sum_{j \neq a} \frac{C_{ar}^2 - C_{jr}^2}{E_a - E_j} \right) (\delta\alpha_r)^2 \dots \text{(A)} \end{aligned}$$

where 'a' and 'b' refer to the highest filled and the lowest empty molecular orbitals of parent aza-aromatics, the primed quantities refer to methyl substituted aza-aromatics and unprimed to aza-aromatics. C_{jr} refers to atomic orbital coefficient of the r^{th} carbon atom in the j^{th} molecular orbital. $\delta\alpha_r$, the change in the coulomb integral of the r^{th} carbon atom, was taken as -0.1β . The molecular orbital energies and atomic orbital coefficients for diazines have been taken from Coulson and Streitwieser⁴ with $\alpha_N = \alpha + 0.5 \beta$ and $\beta_{CN} = \beta$ and the molecular orbital calculation on

1. D. Peters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 646.
2. A. K. Chandra and S. Basu, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1623.
3. H. C. Longuet-Higgins and R. G. Sowden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1404.
4. C. A. Coulson and A. Streitwieser, *Dictionary of π -electron calculations*, 1965, Pergamon Press, London p., 251, 254, 257.

pyridine-1-oxide was done by straightforward method with $\alpha_N = \alpha + 0.5 \beta$, $\alpha_O = \alpha + 2\beta$, α_C' (coulomb integral for carbon attached to nitrogen) = $\alpha + 0.1 \beta$ and all resonance integral being set equal to β . The molecular orbitals for pyridine-1-oxide is given in the appendix.

Hyperconjugative effect: If β_{rs} is the resonance integral of the bond formed between the r^{th} carbon atom of parent aza-aromatics and the s^{th} carbon atom of the methyl group, then the energy change due to hyperconjugative effect can be written as

$$(\Delta E_{ba})_{\text{hyperconj}} = \left(\sum_{\substack{k \neq b \\ k \neq a}} \frac{C_{br}^2}{E_b - E_k} \frac{C_{ks}^2}{E_k - E_a} - \sum_{\substack{k \neq a \\ k \neq b}} \frac{C_{ar}^2}{E_a - E_k} \frac{C_{ks}^2}{E_k - E_b} \right) \beta_{rs}^2 \dots \quad (\text{B})$$

A conjugating methyl group is considered as $-C \equiv H_3$ with the following coulomb and resonance parameters:

$$\alpha_C = \alpha - 0.1 \beta, \beta_{Me} = 2.5 \beta, \alpha_{H_3} = \alpha - 0.5 \beta, \beta_{rs} = 0.7 \beta.$$

The resultant effect of the substituent is obtained by adding the two separate effects and the effect of two or more methyl groups has been considered additive.

The results are set out in Table I, where the column headed by $\Delta\lambda$ is the energy difference converted into wavelength ($m\mu$), calculated by taking $\beta = -23000 \text{ Cm}^{-1}$.

TABLE I

Calculated & experimental spectral shift.

Compound	(ΔE_{ba}) induct	(ΔE_{ba}) hypercon	(ΔE_{ba}) total	$\Delta\lambda(\text{cal})$ $m\mu$	$\Delta\lambda(\text{obs})$ $m\mu$	Ref.
<i>Pyrazine</i> :	$E_b - E_a = -1.6861 \beta$,	$\lambda_{\text{max}} = 261$ (pH-7)				5
2, methyl	+0.01563 β	+0.04155 β	+0.05718 β	9	10	5
2, 5 dimethyl	+0.03126 β	+0.08310 β	+0.11436 β	18	15	5
2, 6 dimethyl	+0.03126 β	+0.08310 β	+0.11436 β	18	14	6
tetramethyl	+0.06252 β	+0.16620 β	+0.22872 β	36	34	6
<i>Pyridazine</i> :	$E_b - E_a = -1.8282 \beta$,	$\lambda_{\text{max}} = 247$ (pH-7)	246 (alcohol) (cyclohexane),			
3, methyl	+0.02972 β	+0.05635 β	+0.08607 β	11.7	5	5
4, methyl	-0.01534 β	+0.01646 β	+0.00112 β	0.1	0	5
3, 4 dimethyl	+0.01438 β	+0.07281 β	+0.08719 β	11.8	8.5	7
4, 5 dimethyl	-0.03068 β	+0.03292 β	+0.00224 β	0.2	3.5	7
<i>Pyrimidine</i> :	$E_b - E_a = -1.8575 \beta$,	$\lambda_{\text{max}} = 243$ (pH-7)				5
4, methyl	-0.01838 β	+0.02715 β	+0.00877 β	1.2	1	8
4, 6 dimethyl	-0.03676 β	+0.05430 β	+0.01754 β	2.4	3	8
2, 4, 6 trimethyl	-0.01303 β	+0.09644 β	+0.08341 β	11.1	9	8
<i>Pyridine-1-oxide</i> :	$E_b - E_a = -1.8139 \beta$,	$\lambda_{\text{max}} = 259$ (N HCl)				9
3, methyl	+0.00728 β	+0.01007 β	+0.01735 β	2.2	6	9
2, 4 dimethyl	+0.00795 β	+0.06701 β	+0.07496 β	10.2	6	9
2, 5 dimethyl	+0.01787 β	+0.02673 β	+0.04460 β	5.9	11	9

5. S. F. Mason, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1247,6. B. Klein and J. Berkowitz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 5160.7. R. H. Horning and E. D. Amstutz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1955, 20, 1069.8. M. J. Kamlet, *Organic Electronic Spectral data*, Vol. I, Interscience (NY), p. 49, 99, 158.9. J. P. Phillips, *Organic Electronic Spectral data*, Vol. IV, Interscience (London), p.32, 78, 127.

TABLE II

Predicted spectral shift

Compound	$(\Delta E_{ba})_{induc}$	$(\Delta E_{ba})_{hyperconj}$	$(\Delta E_{ba})_{total}$	$\Delta\lambda(m\mu)$
<i>Pyrazine :</i>				
2, 3-dimethyl	+0.03126 β	+0.08310 β	+0.11436 β	18
Trimethyl	+0.04689 β	+0.12465 β	+0.22144 β	27
<i>Pyridazine :</i>				
3, 6-dimethyl	+0.05944 β	+0.11270 β	+0.17214 β	23.4
4, 6-dimethyl	+0.01438 β	+0.07281 β	+0.08719 β	11.8
3, 4, 5-trimethyl	-0.00096 β	+0.08927 β	+0.08831 β	11.9
3, 4, 6-trimethyl	+0.04410 β	+0.12916 β	+0.17326 β	23.5
Tetramethyl	+0.02876 β	+0.14562 β	+0.17438 β	23.6
<i>Pyrimidine :</i>				
2-methyl	+0.02373 β	+0.04214 β	+0.06587 β	8.7
5-methyl	+0.03889 β	+0.06912 β	+0.10801 β	14.4
2, 4-dimethyl	+0.00535 β	+0.06929 β	+0.07464 β	9.9
2, 5-dimethyl	+0.06262 β	+0.11126 β	+0.17388 β	23.1
4, 5-dimethyl	+0.02051 β	+0.09627 β	+0.11678 β	15.6
2, 4, 5-trimethyl	+0.04424 β	+0.13841 β	+0.18265 β	24.3
4, 5, 6-trimethyl	+0.00213 β	+0.12342 β	+0.12555 β	16.8
Tetramethyl	+0.02586 β	+0.16556 β	+0.19142 β	25.5
<i>Pyridine-1-oxide :</i>				
2-methyl	+0.01059 β	+0.01666 β	+0.02725 β	3.7
4-methyl	-0.00264 β	+0.05035 β	+0.04771 β	6.5
2, 3-dimethyl	+0.01787 β	+0.02673 β	+0.04460 β	5.9
2, 6-dimethyl	+0.02118 β	+0.03332 β	+0.05450 β	7.4
3, 4-dimethyl	+0.00464 β	+0.06042 β	+3.06506 β	8.7
3, 5-dimethyl	+0.01456 β	+0.02014 β	+0.03470 β	4.4

DISCUSSION

In collecting the observed spectral data given in table I for a comparison with the calculated shift, the results of measurements, made under comparable conditions, have been chosen as far as possible. Agreement between the calculated and experimental shift is fairly good. As no experimental data are available for many of these compounds, the results are given in Table II as predicted spectral shift.

The present calculation shows that the hyperconjugative effect is always bathochromic, but inductive effect may be bathochromic or hypsochromic depending upon the position of the methyl group. In some cases the two effects may almost neutralise each other resulting in a very small shift, as indeed, is the case with 4-methyl substituted pyridazine and pyrimidine. The resultant effect is always bathochromic, as is actually the case.

APPENDIX

Atomic orbital coefficients of pyridine-1-oxide are tabulated as below. The Y-direction is the straight line through nitrogen, oxygen and 4th carbon atom :

Energy Level	Symmetry	C ₁	C ₂	C ₃	C ₄	C ₇
$\alpha+2.753$	S _y	+0.5473	+0.2531	+0.1243	+0.0902	+0.7296
$\alpha+1.812$	S _y	+0.0907	+0.3007	+0.4241	+0.4680	-0.4824
$\alpha+1.051$	A _y	0	+0.5121	+0.4877	0	0
$\alpha+0.8859$	S _y	+0.4781	+0.3076	-0.2364	+0.5336	-0.4307
$\alpha-0.928$	S _y	+0.5771	-0.3135	-0.2548	+0.5493	-0.1971
$\alpha-0.951$	A _y	0	+0.4874	-0.5123	0	0
$\alpha-1.932$	S _y	+0.3547	-0.3862	+0.4300	-0.4451	-0.0902

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